

Diversity and teacher students' positioning in research: Nuances that matter

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How to educate future mathematics teachers to deal with the challenges of diversity in mathematics classrooms continues to be a central concern for practice and research. Through researching the research on mathematics teacher education that addresses equity, justice and diversity in initial teacher education, three different positionings of teacher students were identified: the teacher student as unachieved, recipient and agentic. The nuances in how research positions teacher students are important in themselves, since they allow to challenge implicit assumptions about opportunities to develop a multifaceted sensibility towards diversity in teacher education.

Introduction

In many countries there is an increased attention to equity and inclusion, given the systematic documented failure or deficiencies of some students. Since many students in classrooms are “diverse” —in contrast with the idea of a relatively homogenous student body—, mathematics teachers need to be able to attend to and manage such “diversity” for creating possibilities “for all” to engage in mathematical learning and thus produce expected results. Such possibility of access to learning is seen as a matter of personal and social importance due to the democratic and economic repercussions of not achieving expected levels of competence in mathematics. These desires are often expressed in national educational policies, in the curricular documents in mathematics and in the regulations for (mathematics) teacher education. These are also some of the concerns and arguments that the research concerned with social justice in mathematics education have voiced (Yolcu, 2019).

For the concrete practices of mathematics teacher education, the recognition of “diversity” poses the demand that teacher students need to gain qualifications during their initial training to be prepared to manage diversity when they become teachers. But how such demand is in fact realized in teacher education is an open question. As one turns to research, it is possible to say that most studies on equity, inclusion and diversity are conducted in schools where practicing teachers deal with the multiple challenges of different pupils and their mathematical learning, as Yolcu (2019) confirms. The research often points to

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implications for teacher education as part of their conclusions. However, the research on mathematics teacher education itself addressing diversity is scarce.

Previous socio-political research on initial teacher education (e.g., Nolan, 2011; Wager, 2012) almost exclusively takes the perspective of the teacher educators and prioritizes organisational issues of teacher education or the curricular contents. The main assumption is that teacher students need to be prepared for their future profession and are therefore offered courses, which should educate them to be socially aware and just teachers. In other words, the attention towards the effects of teacher education for managing diversity overshadows the fact that diversity may well be already vividly present in the practices of teacher education and among their participants, and not only on its outcomes.

As a way to start turning the gaze towards the practices of initial teacher education as a site for unfolding the meanings of diversity, equity and inclusion, we examine research in the setting of mathematics teacher education programs that explicitly focus on the political predicaments of “diversity” in a broad sense. That is, empirical research that prioritizes political issues as central elements of initial mathematics teacher education. We examine how teacher students are positioned in the research to cast light on the effects of such positionings in building particular notions of who the teacher student is becoming and the possibilities of action regarding diversity in mathematics education. We pursue the questions of how is research positioning the teacher student with respect to “diversity” and how is research configuring what counts as “diversity” in mathematics teacher education.

Researching positioning in research

This paper presents a study that uses a *researching research* (Pais & Valero, 2012) strategy on literature on mathematics teacher education addressing issues of diversity, inclusion and social justice. Researching research as a methodological strategy is not equivalent to a literature review that maps and describes existing results. Instead, it analyses how research itself builds particular ways of conceiving of its objects and thus shapes what is possible (or not) to see and say concerning a given problem. Thus, inspired in Foucaults’ (1973) discussions on the emergence of human sciences and on critical studies of education (Popkewitz & Brennan, 1998), this strategy points to the very political nature of research, in this case, how teacher education research itself not only captures and represents the world but actively effects power by shaping its concepts, objects, limits and practical possibilities.

The notion of *positioning* is an important tool in our analysis. Positioning in socio-linguistic and cultural psychology terms refers to a discursive phenomenon through which individuals assign to themselves or others a series of attributes (e.g., Davies & Harré, 1990) through the performance of actions (Potter & Wetherell, 1987). In some mathematics education research, positioning is used as an indicator of how power relations organise discourses and how individuals both take up and get assigned different attributes as a consequence of discourses articulated in the interactions of teaching and learning in

classrooms (e.g., Herbel-Eisenmann et al., 2010). The frequently used way of doing this analysis is focusing on the linguistic characteristics of informants' utterances to interpret them in terms of position and positioning.

In our analysis we take a different approach to identify positionings. Taking a Foucaultian stance on discourse to analyse published research texts invites us to conceptualize the positioning of teacher students in terms of the attributes assigned to them in the statements of truth that emerge in the texts. The overall guiding questions were: What is being said about the teacher students and how are they being portrayed? In other words, what are the texts stating about teacher students and diversity? Drawing on Valero and Knijnik (2015) we distinguish three levels of analysis to move from the texts to the identification of positionings: (1) We focus on the level of the *sentences* in the texts that say something about the teacher students, diversity and their relationship. (2) We identify the meaning of the sentences as they express repetitions and differences on what is said about the teacher students, diversity and the relationship between those two. This leads to the identification of *enunciations*. (3) Finally, we identify the larger stories or *statements of truth* that the enunciations express about the teacher students, diversity and their relationship. It is in these statements where we locate the positionings of the teacher students in the discourse unfolded in the research texts.

The empirical material studied is a set of 34¹ published papers in international research journals in English, in the period 2008–2020. The criteria for the selection of studies were (1) that papers should be situated in the context of mathematics teacher education, and focus especially on issues tightly connected to mathematics teacher education, such as course content or projects, documents (curricula, international reports, etc.), teacher educators' work, teaching and experiences, or student teaching; (2) that they contained an empirical component such as interviews, surveys, observations, texts of various kinds, etc., i.e. theoretical/discussion papers were excluded; and (3) that they had a focus on diversity, equity and inclusion, meaning that either an overall aim of the study concerns diversity, or that specific research questions have this focus.

A general characterization of the material shows that 20 papers were about teacher students' learning and their involvement to some extent. The remaining 14 focused on teacher educators' work and reflections, and analyses of course literature and syllabuses. The papers are written by researchers in different geographical locations and the concerns for diversity include race and socioeconomic differences as a matter of social justice in mathematics teacher education; issues of language and cultural differences among teacher students; and the attention to individual needs and dis(ability), language and ethnicity.

¹ Out of the 34 papers that constitute our data set, we only include 21 in the list of references for the sake of space. These 21 texts best illustrate the findings and are marked with * before them.

Positionings of teacher students and diversity

The analysis of the research texts allowed us to, from within the discourse, distinguish three distinct statements regarding teacher students and diversity. We start by formulating the statement and the series of enunciations that compose each positioning. We then illustrate with fragments from the texts the nuances in the attributes that are associated to each positioning.

The unachieved teacher student

Teacher students have deficiencies related to their capacities to be teachers and to their own perception of diversity. The teacher students need to be developed to acquire new desired capacities —beliefs, moral stances, desires. They have to learn more —knowledge and strategies— to be able to fulfill the task of a mathematics teacher that can handle students’ diversity. Knowledge of diversity is insufficient but a precondition for future action. The responsibility of succeeding in this process is on the students’ shoulders. Diversity is encapsulated in forms of knowledge, beliefs and moral stances.

Many mathematics teacher students do not have a capacity to deal with diversity. That capacity is related to their knowledge of mathematics and how they conceptualise issues of diversity, equity and social justice (Max, 2017), as “there is a symbiotic relationship between difficulties with mathematical content and teaching for social justice” (Garii & Appova, 2013, p. 206). But also, teacher students’ beliefs (Simic-Muller, 2015), reflections (Yow, 2012), self-awareness (Yow, 2012), values and ethical standing to appreciate (Goodson-Espy et al., 2016), recognize and act to change (Guerra & An, 2016).

Teacher students need to gain knowledge about diversity as part of their education to be able to cope with the realities and demands of mathematics classrooms. They have to change “conceptions of teaching mathematics for social justice” (Jong & Jackson, 2016, p. 28) and increase their awareness about equity in teaching. Even though they understand both the mathematics and the social justice content, “their ability to integrate both in a single lesson [can be] both inadequate and flawed” (Garii & Appova, 2013, p. 206). Hence, “it is the responsibility of teacher education programs to address these misconceptions and challenge the deficit beliefs” (Simic-Muller, 2015, p. 33) held by teacher students. There is a need to “know more about how [teacher students] conceptualize their role and ability to create equitable environments for their future students” and to study “what considerations [teacher students] make when conceptualizing equitable environments” (Max, 2017, p. 288).

However, the overall responsibility for change lies on the teacher student, because it is him/her who needs to learn the content of teacher education. Therefore, teacher educators need to provide tasks and “assignments that require PSTs to explore social justice problems involving mathematics in a global context” (Goodson-Espy et al., 2016, p. 792) and “examine how well teacher-candidates are able to incorporate [ideas of diversity and] in what ways do the teacher-candidates attempt to approach mathematics content through [diversity] lenses” (Garii & Appova, 2013, p. 200). Importantly, “teacher educators should prepare PTs to decrease oppressive practices and increase liberative [mathematics practices]” (Yow, 2012,

p. 84), and set goals of moral order so that “PSTs [...] come to appreciate individuals within their own communities as valid practitioners of mathematics; and [...] come to understand the responsibility that they, their school districts, and others bear to ensure that all students have equitable opportunities to learn mathematics” (Goodson-Espy et al., 2016, p. 791).

The recipient teacher student

Teacher students are the recipient of teacher educators' actions to provide exposure to different ideas and notions of diversity. Diversity is a content to be learned, but it is the responsibility of teacher education educators and programs to offer opportunities for teacher students to deal with situations where diversity is important. The preparation is not achieved just through knowledge but also through what teacher education programs allow participants—teacher educators and teacher students—to do. Diversity is conceived as the exposure to different ideas on how to deal with pupils' differences.

Teacher educators and teacher education programs bear the responsibility to offer opportunities for teacher students to deal with issues of diversity in mathematics education (Mintos, 2019; Essien, 2014), inclusive education (Guðjónsdóttir & Óskarsdóttir, 2019) and multilingual contexts (Essien, 2014). Even though teacher students “must develop certain processes to teach mathematics through a lens of equity”, teacher educators “might support PSTs to acquire knowledge, scrutinize their beliefs and emotions, and develop interpersonal communication” (Vomvoridi-Ivanovic & McLeman, 2015, p. 86), and be aware of “different views [in the organisation] on how to prepare teacher students for work in inclusive school settings” (Guðjónsdóttir & Óskarsdóttir, 2019, p. 2), which, for instance can happen through rehearsals of instruction and “in-the-moment coaching” (Averill et al., 2016, p. 500). In order for teacher students to develop awareness of equity in teaching, “ample time to discuss authentic issues in diversity [is required]” hence, there is need for teacher educators “to be aware of their own oppressive and liberative teaching practices in doing such work” (Yow, 2012, p. 83).

For this to be achieved, teacher educators need to reflect on “what should happen in teachers' education programs” (Chitera, 2011, p. 236) in order to prepare teacher students for work in diverse contexts. Should, for example, teacher educators “use local languages as they prepare the prospective teachers?” (Chitera, 2011, p. 236). In offering opportunities for teacher students to teach mathematics in multilingual contexts it is of importance how teacher educators pay attention to different “facets of mathematics teacher training [...] and how [these facets] can inform pre-service teacher education” (Essien, 2014, p. 64).

There are “different views [among teacher educators] on how to prepare teacher students for work in inclusive school settings” (Guðjónsdóttir & Óskarsdóttir, 2019, p. 2), and teacher education courses focus on various aspects of diversity, such as disabilities, multilingualism, social justice and on creating learning spaces for all. Hence, if there is no consensus and “teacher educators have different views on how to prepare teacher students to work in inclusive settings” (Guðjónsdóttir & Óskarsdóttir, 2019, p. 11) this can lead to inconsistencies in conceptualisations of inclusion. This, in turn, “can result in confusion and uncertainty

among student teachers. Some might believe that it is not their responsibility to teach all learners and others that there is a special ‘toolbox’ to use for certain types of learners” (Guðjónsdóttir & Óskarsdóttir, 2019, p. 8).

Teacher educators’ awareness of the context of teacher students’ is of importance in offering opportunities to integrate urgent social justice issues in mathematics teacher education, for instance through “focusing on how [the educator] could live out [her] values of social justice [concerning HIV & AIDS] more fully in [her] own practice as a Mathematics teacher educator” (van Laren, 2011, p. 338). Teacher educators have, over the years, gained experiences from teaching diverse contexts that inform the structures and contents in the program, such as language diversity. Therefore, educators need to be aware “of the issues that teachers face and about which teachers might need to be sensitized” (Thompson et al., 2016, p. 7); to take responsibility for “address[ing] the language diversity of their students” and to take into consideration “the role of mathematics teacher educators in this preparation” (Thompson et al., 2016, p. 122). By engaging teacher students in “experiences of culturally responsive mathematics teaching that they could take with them into their own teaching” (Averill et al., 2009, p. 162) and by providing opportunities to interact “with students from various backgrounds in the practicum experience, pre-service teachers will also be able to learn how race, socioeconomic class, and gender could affect a youth’s decision-making and development” (Wang & Apraiz, 2018, p. 41). Learning through experiences from practicum will “serve the student teacher well when he or she teaches a group of culturally diverse students” (Wang & Apraiz, 2018, p. 41).

The agentic teacher student

Teacher students and teacher educators are equal active participants in constructing and experiencing what diversity may mean to develop a different sensibility towards pupils’ differences. Diversity is framed as a sensibility to identify, think about and challenge the many sides and faces of students’ and pupils’ differences.

Teacher students’ previous experiences (Jackson & Jong, 2017) and opinions of how diversity is foregrounded in the program (Çelik, 2018) are central in making sense of diversity in teacher education. Through increasing awareness and collaborative work (Goodson-Espy et al., 2016), and in negotiating dominant educational discourses (Hossain et al., 2013; Farnsworth, 2010) teacher students are agents in constructing and experiencing diversity in mathematics education.

By inviting teacher students to critically reflect on their “own experiences as mathematics learners, the influence of their past mathematics teachers, and their own conceptions about how mathematics should be taught” (Jackson & Jong, 2017, p. 67), they are also invited to challenge and rethink issues of diversity. Teacher students contribute and co-construct meanings of diversity through critical reflections “on issues of equity in the mathematics classroom” (Jackson & Jong, 2017, p. 79). These responses may “not necessarily [be] the desired or ideal” (Jackson & Jong, 2017, p. 71). However, in inviting teacher students to also reflect on “how often the teacher training program provides them with opportunities

for learning how to teach to diverse groups of students" (Çelik, 2018, p. 14), and, in constructing meanings of issues of diversity, the discourses are open for negotiation.

A "challenge for teacher education is to find ways to support pre-service teachers in negotiating these Discourses in ways that engage critical reflection and support a kind of inner dialogue around such contradictions" (Farnsworth, 2010, p. 1485). However, one way can be to listen to what they say. Teacher students contribute with experiences "You don't ask any questions because you are scared that, er, you, you insult the teacher by asking him or her 'why?" (student voice in Hossain et al., 2013, p. 44) and bring to the context of teacher education ways to challenge previous experiences "[...] and what I understand here is that, as a teacher, you need to know all the ways because the, the student might understand one way better. Whereas where I'm coming from, the teacher teaches whichever one he's [sic] comfortable with, and that's it" (student voice in Hossain et al., 2013, p. 44). So, as [teacher students] "are thinking about equitable issues in their emerging practice in terms of access and power" (Max, 2017, p. 293), there is need for teacher education programs to integrate "equity-based teaching strategies in methods courses and allow for opportunities for preservice teachers to think about equity in terms of equality and how they can structure their practices to best support the diverse populations they will inevitably encounter" (Max, 2017, p. 293).

Nuances of positioning that matter

Researching the research in the 34 selected papers allowed us to identify three different statements and related enunciations concerning how the teacher students are positioned in the texts and how notions of diversity is connected to the actual positioning.

The first positioning of the teacher student as *unachieved* does not only point to the notion of lacks in teacher students that need to be filled, but also to the individual responsibility of the teacher student to fill his/her own lacks. In this positioning diversity is also connected to the lack that has to be filled, that is, the main idea navigating in the research is the focus on what "has to be learned". The second positioning of the teacher student as *recipient* has a slightly different turn which acknowledges the responsibility of teacher education –the educators, structures, programs and organisations of the curriculum– to provide opportunities for teacher students to fill their lacks. Notions of diversity do not really differ in these two positionings. What differs is whose actions that are in focus: the lacking teacher student's or the providing teacher educator's. The third positioning of teacher students as *agentive* seems to turn the gaze to the multiple differences among teacher students and teacher educators as a very same site of exploration and source of engagement with diversity. The idea of diversity as a sensibility to notice difference starts from the very same situation and conditions of teacher education. It is not necessarily a lack that needs to be filled for a future practice, but rather a field to explore, truths to negotiate and structures to challenge.

A general observation is that the statements do not coincide with "types of research" that allowed us to categorise the 34 papers in discrete categories. Although some statements

appear strongly in some papers, more than one statement may appear in the same text. This means that there is no reason to characterise some research as intentionally positioning teacher students as *unachieved*, *recipient* or *agentic*. However, there are few of the 34 studies that involve the teacher student to generate a sensibility where the teacher student is not an object of learning or of a teacher education recipient, but that the teacher student is an agentic player. Instead, what we have seen in this analysis is that the teacher students are kind of set in a “passive” role of active knowledge acquirers rather than an active position of critical participants, and diversity is a content to be learned.

Diversity is defined and approached in different ways, and this may have implications for how the teacher student is positioned in research. Approaching diversity as a subject to learn or as sensibility to notice difference hence opens for discussions about future teachers’ autonomy and awareness of the multifaceted nature of teaching and learning of mathematics. We can see that there is a risk that teacher students are expected to learn to know how to teach in diverse classrooms. But they are not taken as agents that could promote a sensibility to possible changes and see multiple differences in students that may be present in a situation. They are not invited to think critically, and to see the diversity that they themselves are a part of. There is also a risk that teacher students stay in a place of “secure knowledge” while diversity is multifaceted, like a diamond and its multiple refractions that cast light, rather than like a simple cube.

If we consider that these small nuances matter, we as researchers could consider conducting research that looks critically at more than the teacher students’ (lack) of (acquisition) of knowledge, but instead at the process of seeing them as capable to develop new changing sensibilities. Positioning the teacher student as agentic requires research where the teacher students are invited into a multifaceted discourse, practice and experience of diversity to be sensible to the nuances. It can be that this indeed happens in many instances of teacher education, but the research has so far not explored this type of position. Research seems to be more interested in attending to the political demands of increasing knowledge in mathematics teacher education, while other very relevant dimensions of diversity may be underprioritized.

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